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Research Article

**DISCUSSION ABOUT THE PRACTICES, KNOWLEDGE AND
PROBLEMS OF RESEARCH BY CLINICAL POST
GRADUATE TRAINEES IN LAHORE**¹Dr. Syed Sajidain Syed, ²Dr Aiman Khan, ³Dr. Bakhtawar Fatima¹BHU Malikhail Upper Kurram Merged District KPK²Federal Government Polyclinic (PGMI)³BHU Phama Sarai, Tehsil Nowshera Virkan, Gujranwala**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

We make this report to check the difficulties or problems facing by those students who are doing training in medical institute. Research which they making are not an easy works when they are also doing their trainings. We take this survey in 2019-2020, with about 98 respondents to know about their problems and issues which they are facing during their research also when their trainings are going on too. We arrange survey with question answers and ask these questions to trainees who are doing their training and also doing researches. After this survey we concluded results that some of trainees show the response as on research, they are paying their expenses by themselves, funding from medical department is very less. And another point is that time they get for research is very less. In this shortage of time it is very difficult for them to arrange all material and complete out their research on time. They also said that they do not have proper training to do these types of tasks as research, so that why it becomes difficult for them. Ratios of these answers was different as respondents those who was getting difficulty in time to complete their research was about 77% and those who can't meet their expenses to complete their task was 78% some of them ask about that they are not properly trained, they did not get training to complete this research was 80% and so on. So after this survey and results we have concluded that they should have complete knowledge about their field and proper practices and training is needed. With these types of researches, problems which are going to get highlighted should be solved. And it is also important to fulfill they requirement which respondents need to complete their tasks.

Key Words: Trainees, barriers, researches, medications, clinics.**Corresponding author:****Dr Syed Sajidain Syed,**

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INTRODUCTION:

This report and survey is arranged to do different task and help to solve problems which persons face to do their research [1]. We also have seen that doctors do not participate in these researches. They do not show any type of interest in these researches [2]. And trainees who are working on researches, make and prepare a proper research was use too with this; they make difficulty to do research because their schooling was not according to this [3]. They do not have any type of experience when they was in schools, so in medical institutes, they face a lot of difficulties to solve their problems and complete their researches [4]. If we see other developing countries, their students do not show interest or they face difficulties to solve and to do research because of not having schooling experiences [5]. That's why they face difficulties to do this research in medical fields [6]. As compare to developing countries, students of well developed countries show response about research methodology. In Pakistan doctors in medical institute who are doing researches showing result as other developing countries [7]. This report shows that the research practices among medical students are deficient [8]. About 55% researchers are facing difficulty to do research and show positive results. 28% are total researchers in the world which we have seen in developing countries [9]. This less ratio of health researchers is very bad situation for developing countries. In Pakistan, students who completed their studies and are able to do researches on health issues are not able to do these researches because of fewer expenses [10]. With this survey issues which are highlighted as less training/practices among students, less knowledge, shortage of time and no or less funding from medical institute should be solved to become

able these researchers to complete their researches and to increase the ratio of researches in whole world as well as in developing countries including Pakistan [11].

METHODOLOGY:

We do this survey in the year of 2019-2020 in a medical institute. Where we ask different questions to respondents who was taking classes and training. We ask them to about study pattern, way of doing training and further processes to become a doctor or researchers. They give us different types of answers with different ratios. We collect results in the form of data. After this survey which was based on question and answers, told the reason of taking this survey to trainees.

RESULTS:

This survey was conducted in the medical institute of Pakistan. We took 98 respondents to whom we ask question about their field and with which they are working. These respondents were about the age of 30-32 years. There was both male female respondents in which the ratio of the males was 55 and female was 43. 21% was those students who was from 2nd year, 30% was from 3rd year, ratio of 4th year students were 31%. They were involve in different study programs. We ask question about which type of facilities they have in these institute. Either they have strong internet connections or not. About 84 out 98 students show positive answers of this question and 14 students was showing negative results because they was not having a good internet connection. One of these questions was how many of them know about unique study methods and any test based on statics. 51% respondents were those who know about unique study methods and only 28% was those who tell us about 2 tests of statics.

Figure: 1 Reasons for not attending Research related workshops

Table: 1

S. No	Practices	Yes n (%)	NO n (%)
1	Attended research related workshop	71 (73.2%)	26 (26.8%)
2	Read medical journals in routine	34 (35%)	63 (65%)
3	Involvement in some research project	39 (40.2%)	58 (59.8%)
4	Paper/poster presentation	8 (8.2%)	89 (91.7%)
5	Publish an Article in a journal	4 (4.1%)	93 (95.8%)

Table: 2

S. No	Barriers	Yes n (%)	No n (%)
1	Poor Access to internet	73 (75.2%)	24 (24.7%)
2	Poor Research orientation in medical college	59 (60.8%)	38 (39.2%)
3	Inadequate access to database/journals	74 (76.2%)	23 (23.7%)
4	Insufficient guidance by supervisors	40 (41.2%)	57 (58.8%)
5	Clinical load gives insufficient time for research	73 (75.2%)	24 (24.7%)

DISCUSSION:

This study about research which was held in a medical institute of Pakistan to check the issues, problems or difficulties students are facing there [12]. We took 98 students to complete our survey by asking multiple questions and receive answers as shortage of time and money, less knowledge about work, no training or practices [13]. Some of them was also facing internet issues during their work. So with the help of these types of survey and studies to solve problems of medical students [14]. In this whole research our main focus was to improve the condition of medical institute and help them to give different ways to make their work much better. About 18% was facing difficulties due to lack of time [15]. 4% was those who was not getting funds from administration and paying their expenses by themselves. This research motivates them to do their task and get aware with new researches and methodology [16]. People living in Pakistan showing less knowledge about research [17]. With counseling we can overcome this issue and make students able to become a good researcher and get good future [18]. Type of research conducted in different countries in developed countries and developing also. In different hospitals of Pakistan these types of surveys or conducted to improve medical researches [19].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that points or error which we have seen in this reports as lack of knowledge, shortage of time and lack of money and many more other type of issues like this are included. So to

overcome all these issues we have to give proper funding, time of research should be increase and also give them proper knowledge about research. When researchers will be relaxed and their requirements will be fulfilled, they can do their work properly and increase the value of researchers in the whole world. With the help of increasing ratio of researchers, value of developing countries will be increased and country will progress automatically.

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